

Sycophancy as a Symptom: A Psychological Needs Perspective on AI's Relational Trap

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The public conversation about AI and wellbeing has been dominated by a particular framing: AI as companion. Conversational AI systems were rapidly adopted as confidants, emotional support tools, and surrogate listeners, with some platforms explicitly marketing AI companionship as a remedy for loneliness, driven by commercial incentives to maximize user engagement. Perry (1) and Cheng et al. (2) demonstrate what happens when this framing meets optimization: models trained through reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) produce sycophantic outputs, affirming users roughly 50% more than humans do, even when the user's actions are harmful. The consequence, as Cheng et al. show, is reduced prosocial behavior and inflated moral self-assessment. We agree with Perry that sycophancy poses a serious risk. We suggest, however, that the phenomenon reflects something deeper than a training problem: it reflects the consequences of positioning AI within a relational role it cannot genuinely occupy.

Dweck's (3) unified theory of motivation identifies several core human psychological needs: the needs for acceptance, competence, predictability, control (autonomy), trust, self-esteem and self-coherence. These needs differ in the kind of support they require. Some, such as acceptance and trust, depend on the perceived presence of another mind capable of genuine care. Others, such as competence and autonomy, can be supported through structured tools, guided practice, and cognitive scaffolding. We have argued that responsive support varies in which needs it addresses

and how deeply it engages the recipient's sense of self (4), and that AI's distinct, non-human qualities can serve needs that relational framing obscures (5).

This distinction clarifies why sycophancy is not merely a training artifact. When AI is positioned as fulfilling needs for connection and emotional validation, users bring relational expectations to the interaction. The system, optimized for approval, meets those expectations with agreement. Sycophancy emerges at the intersection of the human tendency toward anthropomorphism and machine optimization (6) — RLHF acts as a mirror, exposing a pre-existing need for validation. The reinforcement contingencies are strongest precisely when the interaction is framed as relational, because the reward signal, user satisfaction, aligns with affirmation rather than accuracy.

A different pattern is emerging as AI shifts from passive, conversational systems toward agentic ones — systems such as Claude Code that hold context, execute multi-step tasks, scaffold structured reasoning, and render complex processes predictable and comprehensible. When people interact with such systems for problem-solving or skill development, the interaction is organized around different needs: competence, autonomy, self-directed mastery. The reinforcement contingencies shift. The user's goal is not to feel validated but to make progress, and the system's value is measured by whether it helped the user think or act more effectively. Weinstein et al. (8) found that AI-based listening increased autonomy satisfaction without reducing loneliness, suggesting that these pathways operate independently. AI in mental health can provide tools designed around therapeutic objectives, such as skill-building, Socratic questioning, and structured self-reflection, which are less susceptible to the sycophancy dynamics Perry describes, because the interaction does not rest on emotional affirmation.

None of this diminishes the urgency of Perry's concern. Sycophancy in relationally framed AI is a genuine risk, and Cheng et al.'s data make the scope of that risk concrete. But the current discourse evaluates AI primarily against relational benchmarks: warmth, empathy, connection. Psychology has the theoretical tools to broaden this evaluation. When the self that seeks validation and the self that seeks growth are in conflict, determining whose interests to serve is a question for psychology and policy alike. Clark (7) has argued that humans extend their minds through tools; AI may be the most consequential such extension. The field's task is not only to document how AI distorts social judgment when it imitates a companion, but to

investigate the forms of cognitive and therapeutic support that become possible when it does not.

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